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Unveiling the Past: Palimpsestic Memory in *All the Lives We Never Lived*

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Abstract:

This paper explores the broader scheme of the contradictory concept of memory and history interspersed in *All the Lives We Never Lived* by Anuradha Roy. The study entails a comprehensive reading of this South Asian novel utilising Max Silverman's concept of palimpsestic memory. It focuses on the interconnectedness of memory, history, and temporality in a narrative that operates in the context of two spaces, India and Dutch-held Bali. The mobility between these spaces shapes the experiences of Gayatri and Myshkin, the mother-son duo. Roy's incorporation of varied allusions and intertextualities maps out a significant temporal journey from pre-independence India and Dutch-held Bali during the 1930s to post-independence India. Myshkin is shown writing his memoir, recapitulating his lost past in 1992. This study explores the superimposed images of memory narrative from personal and collective stances, indicating its palimpsestic nature. Finally, this study incorporates transnational memories, challenging the traditional confines of national memory.

Keywords: Palimpsestic Memory; Travelling Memory; Temporality; Historical Memory; Identity; Transcultural Memory; Metafiction.

Introduction

Anuradha Roy's *All the Lives We Never Lived* is a historical fiction written in an elegiac form, adeptly interweaving historical allusions to individual memory. Through the character's consciousness, this interwoven narrativity efficaciously shows the implication of fragmented reality and time upon the psyche of the one who moves between countries and the one who has an eventual transformation over a temporal shift. Even though the story is replete with allusions and historical time stamps situated throughout, the plot transcends to some plurality of events, merging the personal with the collective, going beyond the historical segmented time frames. The protagonist, Myshkin Rozario, is a sixty-year-old horticulturist who seeks to understand his mother's true nature and the reality behind his perception of her. Through memory and active recollection, along with interpreting the past via records, letters, and literature, he strives to reconcile with the trauma of his abandonment by her. Throughout this narrative journey, he carefully balances both material and spiritual reasoning. His mother left him when he was a mere nine-year-old child. His opinion about his mother was formed as he was tortured with the whispers from society that tried to sneer at a child whose mother had chosen to start anew in Bali with another renowned German artist, Walter Spies. Naturally, this little kid, Myshkin, had enough resentment for his mother because, for him, she was just a selfish woman who left her son and never returned.

However, as he ages, he intends to have steady documentation of his past life from sensory memory to find meaning in his bleak and hazy past. Moreover, he was now delivered a package with dozens of letters, a testament to the correspondence between Gayatri Rozario and their family friend and perhaps the only person in contact with Gayatri, Lisa McNally. These letters become a gateway to Gayatri's version of the story, which remains untainted by societal prejudices and assumptions. This memory retrieval and remediation becomes an attempt by Myshkin Rozario to eventually come to terms with his mother's individualistic spirit

and her reasons for such reckless actions. The main characters in the novel are Gayatri Rozario, Myshkin Rozario, his father Nekchand Rozario, his grandfather Bhavani Chand Rozario, also known as Batty Rozario, and the fictional town of Muntazir, located near the Himalayas. Additionally, the story features the depiction of Dutch-held Bali through Gayatri's letters and paintings. Spatial mobility exists between countries, such as Muntazir in India and Dutch-held Bali in the 1930s. The narrative has integrated history with allusions to national and cultural memory, which is how palimpsestic memory operates.

Literature Review

An overarching theme in *All the Lives We Never Lived* is the concept of freedom, which encompasses both personal and political dimensions. Gayatri's quest for artistic expression and emancipation reflects the broader struggles for autonomy faced by individuals and nations. Her departure from her family can be interpreted as an act of self-liberation and a form of exile, shedding light on the sacrifices and consequences associated with the pursuit of one's dreams.

Additionally, the novel explores the theme of identity through Myshkin's fragmented memories and the influence of his mother's decisions on his sense of self. A strong correlation and similitude can be witnessed in the intertwining of memory and identity. Myshkin's grappling with his recalcitrant impressionable understanding of his mother and her foibles as he was abandoned at the age of nine by her finds a steady transformation and reconciliation through nostalgia, memory readings and mnemonics, its epistolary variance through letters and, finally, his own introspective readings of literary, allusive, intertextual life and fiction. He finally could come to terms with the truth behind her mother's fleeting and unbridled adventurous spirit since she sought an individuality that Myshkin, as a boy, could not understand. Still, he later saw that resonate in his moulded identity, leaving a conventional path and becoming a horticulturist. As an artist himself, while Myshkin becomes a man, he acquiesces to his mother's narrative struggle that screams of a bildungsroman narrative genre,

where against the postcolonial, nationalistic fervour of a background, Gayatri assumes the elevated character of an artist, making it a tale about a search for an artistic persona. Roy's narrative style, which alternates between different perspectives and times, underscores the fluidity and complexity of personal identity.

The novel is set against a tumultuous period in India's history, seamlessly weaving in significant historical events. The British Raj, the Indian independence movement, and World War II are skillfully integrated into the narrative, lending depth to the characters' challenges and choices. Chattopadhyay (2023), in his paper, tries to examine Anuradha Roy's novel *Sleeping on Jupiter* from super-exploitative Neo-liberal capitalism and through Gayatri Chakraborty Spivak's concept of 'premodern', he delineates a compelling narrative on the problematised correlation between memory and space. It problematises the idea evident in one of the lines from the novel *Sleeping on Jupiter* that Chattopadhyay cites in his paper where the character Nomi feels certain because of a recurrent dream and she feels "I was in the place the boat had brought me to when I was six or seven" (Roy *All the Lives* 34). Chattopadhyay reads into these instances from the novel as a testament to "partially recalled cherished memory laced with trauma" (p. 217); this novel also finds it under the aegis of palimpsestic narrative, as does *All the Lives We Never Lived*.

In almost all of her novels, Roy has unequivocally promoted the search for self, encompassing a philosophic discourse around feminism, individuality, eco-anthropogenic reality, the trauma of dislocation and migration, memory and trauma affectivity at the cumulative contextualisation. There has been a scholarly exploration of the dichotomous relationship between the idealistic patriarchal ideology and Gayatri Rozario's feminine individualism. According to Ayesha Farooq et al. (2018), in their work titled "Breaking the Patriarchal Mould: A Feminist Analysis of Anuradha Roy's *All the Lives We Never Lived*", this novel depicts a critical understanding of how colonialism and patriarchy intersect to reinforce

power imbalances. This paper examines how Roy uses language, narrative structure, and symbolism to convey feminist messages about power and agency. Basing their argument on feminist theorists ranging from Bell Hooks and Judith Butler to historical figures like Amrita Sher-Gil and Begum Rokeya, they have situated the novel's engagement with more significant debates in feminist and postcolonial studies. It invites readers to consider how gender shapes our experiences and identities. Farooq and others lent a significantly prolific scholarly voice, suggesting that *All the Lives We Never Lived* (2018) becomes instrumental in examining the complex intersections of gender and colonialism and exploring the possibilities of resistance and solidarity in the face of oppression.

Two more relevant papers written on Roy's novel *All the Lives We Never Lived* are Suganya and Dr A. Selvaraj's "Quest for Self in the novel *All the Lives We Never Lived* by Anuradha Roy" (2021) and "Exploration of Trauma in Anuradha Roy's *All the Lives We Never Lived*" By Priya Dalal and Dr Anupriya Roy Srivastava. So, all these scholastic studies have mainly explored the imminent themes of feminism, self and other narratives and the parochial and postcolonial discussion on trauma, memory and space.

Roy's other novels of prominence, like *An Atlas of Impossible Longing*, *The Earthspinner* or *Sleeping on Jupiter*, find their extensive interpretive readings in anthropogenic climate change or migration and dislocation memory climate in Karen, and Gnanadurai's (2023) paper, or migration and dislocation memory in Dalal and Srivastava's "The Trauma of Dislocation: Portrayal of Migration and Memory in Anuradha Roy's *An Atlas of Impossible Longing*.". Cristina Nikolae, in her study and papers, has expounded on the novels *All the Lives We Never Lived* as a chapter and *The Earthspinner* as a paper. She likens the two stories and their narrative characters and treatment by stating that Roy's *All the Lives We Never Lived* treats the narrative in a similar transgressive pattern structuring a connective turn between varied chronotopic boundaries as Cristina expounds in her paper, stating, "temporal and spatial

coordinates, blurring the boundary between past [...] and present, between here and there, inner world and the world outside the self, but also between the fictitious and the real” (Nicolae 116).

This present study has been intended to transcend these discussions even further by taking cues from Silverman’s (2013) theoretical idea of palimpsestic memory, which would entail the postmodern literary narrative exposition in this novel and the fragmented historical and temporal structure giving the novel a summative understanding from the double narrative of Myshkin and Gayatri’s quest for self in a cultural cornucopia of a war-torn space struggling two historic setups merging India with Dutch-held Bali and what transpires to be a novel of memory, nation, culture and temporal mobility and palimpsest.

Theoretical Framework

According to Max Silverman, palimpsestic memory can be defined as the condensation of different spatiotemporal traces to describe these interconnections and define the poetics and politics of this composite form.

takes the form of a superimposition and interaction of different temporal traces to constitute a sort of composite structure, like a palimpsest, so that one layer of traces can be seen through, and transformed by, another [...] producing a chain of signification which draws together disparate spaces and times. (Silverman 13)

Here, Silverman takes Walter Benjamin’s concept of ‘constellation’ to indicate history as not necessarily a linear history but with the overlapping of different moments in time having a connection between them, finding a superimposed palimpsestic model. This idea has a swift association with Ricoeur’s philosophic engagement with history, memory, and forgetting. In his sense of hermeneutic and phenomenological study, temporality and memory have a unique aspect that is not just solitary but also imaginative and fictive.

In her novel, Anuradha Roy portrays an amalgamation of temporality, memory, history, and imagination to produce an effect of conglomerated identity and self. The text *All the Lives We Never Lived* deals with the theme of freedom, which is conflicted between two versions. One is Nekchand Rozario's abstinence-driven, sanctified patriotic ideas of freedom of one's country, which are resounded in his philosophy as he writes in his newspaper articles, boasting of his sense of austerity as a mark of enlightened emancipation. In stark contrast to Nekchand's austere tendencies of solemnity, his wife Gayatri Rozario's idea of liberation is not contingent on country, politics, and societal dictates. She aspires for artistic freedom that assures her a place where she can move beyond the societal demands and duties that a woman is bound by. She wants to paint in a land of the unknown without accountability to anything or anyone. This sense of nonchalant aspiration motivated her to leave her family and past and migrate to Dutch-held Bali with Walter Spies, the famous German artist.

In her interview, Anuradha Roy admits that *All the Lives We Never Lived* has been written in a fashion to mingle history and memory in its fictional variance. In its allusive interpolation of characters, events, and tropes throughout the text, the fictional and the nonfictional undertones, in tandem, effectively provoke the readers to read into some fragmented reality. This ambiguity creates a postmodern scenario of intertextuality and pastiche in its treatment of themes and characters. In contrast, palimpsest acts as a literary trope that serves the idea of superimposed ideas of events, documents, and information getting overwritten innumerable times, adding new layers to the existing parchment. This patchwork imagery is perhaps the line of thought that motivated Max Silverman, one of the memory studies stalwarts, to introduce the concept of *Palimpsestic memory*. In this novel, the portrayal of an individual or personal memory involves both active remembering and radical forgetting. This process, along with reflections on national, cultural, and collective memory, allows the

protagonist, Myshkin Rozario, and his mother, Gayatri Rozario, to engage in a process of self-expression through the act of memorialisation.

Mnemonics in Temporality: Mediating and Remediating the Past

In the recent online discussion of the Memory Studies Association, a significant event that has brought together scholars, researchers, and students in the field of Memory Studies, the topic of “Museums, Memory and Temporality” was explored. Dated 28 October 2021, the brief outline and the base point for debate propagates the idea that, beyond the conventional notion of temporality, it is neither neutral nor natural. This convention is intended to use this argument to establish the implications of temporality in memory and history. A significant point of discussion in relation to this argument is that history as a discipline, more often than not, clearly demarcates the past and the present. On the other hand, memory follows a naturally fluid temporal course instead of being just subjective, affective, and personal in its tendency. Since temporality has no fixed determinacy in memory, transcultural memory and travelling memory or palimpsestic memory from diverse points of concurrence emphasise the heterogeneity in thoughts and identity depending on memory.

Anuradha Roy utilises the trope of intertextuality and repeated allusions throughout the novel to give each character their extended dimensions. One such allusive portrayal of another literary genius in a subtle fashion is the description of *Na Hanyate*, a book by Maitreyi Devi. Incidentally, Myshkin turned out to be the mouthpiece of the authorial intention, suggesting that both Maitreyi Devi and Gayatri Rozario were contemporaries. It tries to indicate the possibility that Gayatri perchance had an encounter with her in 1926 during her visit to Rabindranath Tagore’s school in Santiniketan. As Myshkin reads Maitreyi Devi’s novel, finding it in his mother’s possessions, he realises that through her transgression, Gayatri has given Maitreyi Devi’s caged subservience a new sense of hope. With a more objective perspective, Myshkin is able to assess his troubled past without being overwhelmed. This

clarity allows him to understand his mother's fervent desire for a new identity that transcends the limitations imposed on her by societal constraints.

The blending of fictional reality with narrative reference points reflects the concept of palimpsest in the context of the novel. It is a series of events in memory and history that get superimposed and rewritten over space and time. It does not get effaced out altogether, emphasising the continuity and interconnectedness of memory and history. A new idea to an existing past nuanced in the act of individual affective self-reflexivity allows the readers and the characters to traverse through this fragmented relativity, feeling connected to a larger narrative.

I have chosen the term 'palimpsestic memory' to discuss this hybrid form because, of all the figures which connect disparate elements through a play of similarity and difference (analogy, metaphor, allegory, montage and so on), the palimpsest captures most completely the superimposition and productive interaction of different inscriptions and the spatialisation of time central to the work of memory that I wish to highlight. (Silverman 15)

Although Silverman focuses on violence and trauma within the framework of palimpsestic memory, specifically in relation to Francophone Holocaust fiction and memory narratives, this paper explores South Asian textual reality. It examines interconnected allegorical references to national history, mythology, and the fictional representation of remembrance and forgetting, emphasising the mediation of both individual and cultural memory.

However, the principle of the superimposition of different traces to condense surface and depth, present and past, and the visible and the invisible remains a powerful way of envisaging the work of memory.⁵² It implies a psychic rearrangement of space (Silverman 46)

The composite imagery thus becomes a space for dual existence. Through the trace of the past, the present finds an innovative set of superimposed interpretations encompassing both the past retrospective image and its present, nuanced, rewritten version. In the novel, we find this constellation or composite imagery as we see mobility through temporal narrative changes from the 1930s till current reality and over space in the travels and their memorialisation by Gayatri, initially oral storytelling to her son Myshkin and later in her letters to Lisa McNally. This epistolic mnemonic process in the form of letters effectively encapsulates her inner turmoil with her immediate past, her lived experiences. It mirrors her subsequent associative encounters with the socio-political changes and events from World War II and the Dutch invasion. She and her innocuous, observant memorialisation and recount of those recorded events thus find a record of simultaneously micro-history embedded within a grand narrative. This palimpsestic memory encapsulated in the postmodern historiographic trope of stabilised dual presence is owing to the all-pervasive nature of memory remediation going beyond isomorphic accounts alone.

Historical fiction and memory

As we read into the existing literature of memory studies, we come across a significant exploration of the distinction between history and memory. During the twentieth century, specifically in French sociology, beginning with Émile Durkheim and ending with Maurice Halbwachs, we can witness the clear demarcation between the two disciplines. Halbwachs distinguishes between historical and collective memory, which proves to be a significant turning point in memory studies as it was emerging and developing into what has turned out to be an indispensable discussion point in philosophy, psychology, sociology, and literary discourses.

Another instance of the significance of facts over lived experiences that comes in the form of personal memory is depicted in Myshkin's self-rebuttal when he contemplates falling

back on documented dates and figures to recollect a particular episode from his past. “Yesterday, I paused in my writing and drew up, a calendar, I had to use reasoning rather than memory to do this” (Roy *All the Lives* 117) and through this quote, the author tries to clearly distinguish the chunk of remembrances that are backed up by facts and documents in contrast to those which are purely memory. In *Proust et les Signes*, Deleuze opines that in Proust’s oeuvre, it is not time or memory but truth that is at stake.

Soon after Gayatri left during the monsoon of 1937, disavowing all her positional responsibility as a homemaker and mother for her travel to Bali on a self-discovery journey, Myshkin’s father, Nek Chand Rozario, decides to give another austere practice a chance. So, he decides to renounce family and house and go on a pilgrimage, travelling from Patna, Lumbini, Nalanda, to Ajanta Ellora and beyond up to Burma (presently Myanmar) and even Ceylon (presently known as Sri Lanka), following the path of Buddha and Hiuen Tsang. He wants to go on this arduous journey seeking truth, truly live as a Buddhist monk devoid of money, living off begging like monks, and meditating along the way. However, all these declaiming and saintly pursuits end in a row of tragedy. He retraces his way back to his family once the journey becomes too rocky, for he cannot find shelter or food out of charity, as he is not a Brahmin. People showed their reservations about granting him the same value as a monk or a saint of a different stature or caste might have secured. However, while he was on his journey, he wrote regularly to Myshkin’s grandfather with a few lines to spare for Myshkin. In one of these letters, he wrote that while taking shelter in Kashi (now Varanasi), his father wrote about the socio-political issue of being poor and one of low or questionable caste or religious identity. He was an atheist who had sworn allegiance to his country’s freedom, and his knowledge was the religion he followed. The charitable places at Benares, ruled mainly by caste, treated him as a beggar with no respect or food, unlike other saints and monks of a Brahminical birth identity. This little social commentary through this minute detail becomes a

narrative depiction of social history amidst personal history, getting mediated through a parchment of memory in the form of a letter.

Myshkin then narrates his mother's letters, which are strictly addressed to him. These letters were a paradigm of geographical maps, storyland fantasies, promising a future in a utopic vision painted by an artist that would prove to be this was a new land beyond Myshkin's imagination, so they became a medium of storytelling and desire and reveries of a foreign land with a usual motherly warmth he so missed. He describes the postage and stamps on the letters with the Nederlandsch-Indie stamp as if they were all the way from the Netherlands. He stated the historical information of Bali being a Dutch colony at the time and how that transpired into letters and telegram services as if a country, on the whole, changed its exact geographical location and got replaced with a new place of different origin, topography, and direction on a map.

This diary turns out to be more than just memorabilia. It consists of every facet of Gayatri Rozario involving her past and present. It started with her childhood vacationing with her father on a trip to Bali to see or have a serendipitous encounter with Rabindranath Tagore, who was travelling to Java, Sumatra, and Bali on a similar voyage. The diary had her chance encounter with Tagore when the literary stalwart took notice of her innocuous nature and asked her to sit beside him, a rare opportunity for Gayatri, which might have been one of the early stimulating factors in helping her grow up as an artist. Gayatri even listed out her groceries from her household chores in this diary, along with the wages paid for services and a domestic information entry. Another few pages in the journal consist of Myshkin's medicine routines and courses for his convulsions and fever, shedding some light on her motherly duties. It had magazine clippings out of her fancy for some art or some sheer frivolity, and yet another item was a matinee ticket to the movie *The Kid*. The movie ticket symbolised her rebellious defiance

in contrast to her husband's admonition of these entertainments, going against the culture and sanctity of an Indian nationalist who only found life to have value in austerity and simplicity.

Moreover, she filled up the pages with culinary recipes, be it Kheer scented with Oranges or Begum Farhan's pulao. There were lots of pictures as pit stops to every event from her life — a photograph with her father when she was blooming as a reflective, liberal thinker and individual under his excellent tutelage, some stranger uncle from Karachi, Banno Didi, her house help, and even her neighbour's kids or the kid of their drivers like Dinu, Raju, Mantu, Lambu, and Golak. In these myriads of snippets of her memory, she left her husband's trace out of the pages of this memoir of life. Again, the diary becomes the focal point where history, memory, and pastiche merge to give an image of a postmodern relic with a fragmented self at its outset.

Postmodern fragmented Self, Pastiche, Memory

In the article titled "Crumbs of Memory: Tracing the 'more-than-representational' in Family Memory," Maria Tumarkin makes a point of situating intergenerational memory in the context of representational and non-representational memory. By that, she wants to pontificate on the mnemonic mediation of memory involving encoding and decoding and how that can be intentional or organic. "We are passed on our family's history not merely as a collection of stories and artefacts but also as what Eva Hoffman (2005) calls 'emanations' that are always on the verge of 'erupting in flashes of imagery' (p. 9)" (Tumarkin 311). In the text, Myshkin, while trying to unravel memories of his lost past intertwined with his mother's past, gets frequently visited by past intergenerational ruminations.

Dr Avishek Parui, in his work *Culture and the Literary: Matter, Metaphor and Memory*, delves into the idea of remembering and forgetting and how perceptively they have their inherent way of operating within human minds. He attaches equal significance to both remembering and forgetting. Drawing from the idea of mind displacement as Freud had

initially propagated with the psycho-structural process, it can be witnessed that with the act of forgetting, there is a persistent mode of effacement either motivated by social or political manipulation or just a personal neural process that tries to omit some information to give space to some other encoded data. Much of this mechanism comes from Joseph La Deoux's idea of chunking.

War against Germany was declared by Britain and then India on September 1939 but Dinu was to leave for boarding school and his father planned a send-off nothing would stop, not even war. It was to be a concert. (Roy *All the Lives* 196)

Here, the extract talks explicitly about the historical implications of war on the personal lives of the minor characters in this novel. Roy handles the micro and macro history and memory through this subtle touch of intricate personal storytelling, blending the individual with the collective. Ambivalence in fictional narrativity is one of the significant tenets of postmodern narrativisation. This text can be critically interpreted while drawing upon fragmented narrativity and ambivalence. This text is replete with historical and cultural instances indicating fictional historicity that has been merged over space and time. It is this nature of resonance that Dr. Parui hints at in his seminal work on memory studies when he quotes David Lodge, who studies how narrative literature invariably fluctuates over space and time, "experiencing as well as articulating ambivalence" (Parui 99).

Pastiche and Memory in Cultural Studies and Art History

The postmodern cultural critique has received significant attention in academic discourse. As a term coined by Frederic Jameson, Pastiche refers to an aesthetic mode characterised by the imitation and juxtaposition of various styles, genres, and historical periods without any originality or critical engagement. On the other hand, memory is a rich and complex concept encompassing individual experiences and collective recollections of the past. The interplay

between these two concepts represents an essential site for understanding contemporary culture and society.

According to Jameson, the prevalence of pastiche in postmodern culture is related to the loss of historical consciousness and critical thinking caused by late capitalism. He argued that pastiche is a form of nostalgia for an undefinable past while lacking any meaningful engagement with it. This cultural logic flattens creativity and innovation, where originality gives way to imitation and repetition. Nostalgia as a theme, as proposed by Svetlana Boym, does not go along the retrospective lines alone but instead drifts towards the prospective or anticipatory tendency. In her article “Nostalgia and Its Discontents,” published in *The Hedgehog Review Critical Reflections on Contemporary Culture, Summer 2007, The Uses of the Past Essays issue*, Svetlana Boym, in one of the three crucial points of discussion regarding nostalgia, explicates a specific nature of nostalgia. She states that, even though nostalgia looks back towards the past, it also looks forward to an imminent future. In her words, “The fantasies of the past, determined by the needs of the present, have a direct impact on the realities of the future” (Boym 14). Thus, nostalgia is not bound by past temporal essence only and has an immediate impact on determining the future. In the novel, Anuradha Roy emphasises this trope of recurrent use of individual memory and history, entrenched in intertextual historical resonances. Initially, it is through the narration of Myshkin’s experience and understanding of his mother, Gayatri Rozario, over the years. As he ages, he takes recourse to literature, be it the famous novel by Maitreyi Devi titled *Na Hanyate* or his mother’s journal writings and even his own stint with diary entries. In the mnemonic intertextual reading of *Na Hanyate*, he finds that Amrita's character becomes a fictional representation of her mother’s individuality. Her association with German artist Walter Spies finds a cord of similitude in Mircea Eliade, the male character who is the protagonist of this interracial love story, *Na Hanyate*, based on actual events in Maitreyi Devi’s life. It can be observed how facts and fiction overlap, as one

understands that palimpsests, memory, and history are effaced and superimposed like patchwork on parchment paper.

However, this view has been contested by some scholars who argue that parody still exists in postmodern times but takes on different forms than in the preceding ages in the theoretical discipline. One such condition is through animated aesthetics, which can result in parodies resistant to dominance. While some scholars like Jameson view pastiche as a form of evisceration or “blank parody,” others like Dyer see it as a more complex cultural mode that offers critical and transgressive potential.

In another instance from the novel, the themes of cultural pastiche and allusive palimpsest become prominent. Evidently, when Myshkin attempts to recount Gayatri's life experiences as recorded in her diary entries, it evokes this quality of allusive palimpsest. One particular segment reflects her early travelogue from childhood. While travelling with her father, she had a fortuitous opportunity to meet Tagore and Walter Spies. Gayatri often shared this memory with young Myshkin before her departure. She fondly remembered a boat ride in 1927 when she was seventeen, accompanied by her father, Agni Sen, on a lake in Bali. This marked her first encounter with the renowned German artist and musician, Walter Spies, who introduced her and her father to dance performances, concerts, beaches, and painting schools, immersing them in the rich tapestry of Balinese art and culture. Spies would narrate the stories behind the dances, which echoed the mythological figures of Rama, Sita, Hanuman, and Ravana—all characters well-known to Gayatri, given their roots in Indian Hindu mythology. However, she was intrigued by the fact that Balinese natives regarded these narratives as authentic to their own cultural and epic history. This instance illustrates the concepts of pastiche and palimpsest, presenting a cosmopolitan or altered history and reality that transcends the boundaries between two nations and consciousnesses. In an interview published in *The Punch Magazine*, Roy says:

One of the things that struck me powerfully when working on this book, and reading the travelogue in Bengali about Bali by Suniti Kumar Chatterji, was the cosmopolitanism and curiosity. These were travellers in 1927, yet the conversations they strike up in faltering Dutch, Malay, and French are so astonishing — even just the effort of it. In one section of Tagore’s letters from Java, he talks about finding himself on a longish car journey with the Raja of Karangasem, a province in Bali... Then, reports Tagore, the Raja began to rattle off all the synonyms for ocean in Balinese, and once he had exhausted those, he started on the names of Hindu deities — rapturous that the words and names had the same Sanskrit root. (Roy “Anuradha Roy: Past forward” 2018)

The discussion of pastiche and memory highlights the ongoing tension between tradition and innovation in the cultural sphere. While Jameson’s critique emphasises how postmodern aesthetics may erase history and differences, some scholars argue that pastiche does not act as a totalising force to suppress creativity and originality completely. Instead, it offers possibilities for constructing cultural memories by consciously engaging with various styles, genres, and historical periods. Thus, to understand how artistic practices connect to collective memory, one needs to exercise critical thinking in order to know how society constructs memory while also recognising how individual memories shape broader cultural narratives.

Postmodern Alterity in Response to Temporality and Memory

The heterogeneous idea of transcultural memory goes beyond the rigid nature of traditional historicity. Historical understanding depends on factual and documented evidence of past events. And understanding both individual and collective memory often shifts focus from grand narratives to micro-narratives, seeking a sense of relative authenticity. Readers can uncover a

liminal temporality in these narratives, merging past narration with unresolved elements through mnemonic devices such as letters, journals, oral storytelling, music, paintings, and memoirs. Through a self-aggrandising introspective procedural excess, one can state an essential yet elusive detail that can never be found in the official history and archives. In the text, Anuradha Roy strictly depends on this process of memory writing through intertextual and postmodern pastiche.

Jorge Louis Borges (p.15) writes about the extratemporal point of convergence, which consists of all the points in “The Aleph,” and laments that language cannot do justice in representing simultaneity in its entirety. Thus, through the character of Myshkin Rozario and his constant obsession with memory writing and rewriting, the author tries to depict the importance of documentation and mediation of personal or collective memory from different viewpoints. In the novel, there are letters by Gayatri Rozario emphasising her version of an intertwining story and journey. Then we have Myshkin, the abandoned son of her mother, and his version of his past, present, and imminent future over a spewed idea of a long-lost past in the embodiment of his mother’s true self.

Conclusion

In Anuradha Roy’s novel *All the Lives We Never Lived* (2019), the clash of history and memory is at the forefront, where personal experiences intertwine with collective or cultural memory. The story unfolds against the backdrop of the tumultuous twentieth century in India. India had to participate in a war not of its own, and then suddenly gained independence from colonial rule. The concept of space, alongside time, plays a crucial role in shaping the diversity within identity and memory across culture, space, and time. This narrative's historical and memory timelines in its fictional representations unearth new meanings that reflect prevailing hegemonic thoughts and ideas. The novel delves into the character Myshkin’s desire to chronicle his personal history, aiming to comprehend his connection to the lost past and how it

influences his present life and memory. The evocative representations through letters, geographical landscapes, historical artefacts, and war anecdotes blend personal and collective experiences, with the geographical borders between India and Bali adding a transcultural and transnational dimension. The intertwined stories of Walter Spies, a German artist, and Gayatri, an Indian artist pursuing artistic freedom, blur the boundaries between micro and macro history through transcultural and palimpsestic memory. By incorporating postmodern pastiche as a prominent narrative device, the author skilfully employs temporal juxtaposition and explores themes such as acculturation, individuality, female subjectivity, diaspora, mysticism, and the struggle with fragmented identity.

While the existing literature on this novel discusses critical explorations of women's emancipation, the process of self-discovery, migration, memory, trauma, and ecological awareness, this paper advances the discourse further. Building on Silverman's concept of palimpsestic memory and examining the postmodern plurality present in the narrative instances—such as Myshkin's memoir writing, Gayatri's letters, diary entries, and paintings—this paper identifies a dynamic pattern in the past that is not absolute, highlighting their collective intertextual references. Myshkin expresses a desire to visit Bali later in life to experience the cultural time and richness that Gayatri encountered during her lifetime in the historically significant era of the 1930s, when Bali was under Dutch rule. This retrospective reminiscence and its present manifestation or pining for that experience reflect the authorial intent. The author intended to remediate history and transform memory into a narrativity that possesses a layered, palimpsestic fluidity. Manifestly, memory and space move and gather a recurrent interpretation over time. The letters, myths, and historical accounts of war, along with the geographical similarities and disparities between India and Bali, intertwine the personal and political narratives. In alignment with Tagore's advocacy for cosmopolitanism, this paper examines these effective representations within the context of a fluid memory novel.

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